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By

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ABSTRACT

No one can imagine life without water, it is a most essential natural resource for the existence of life. Water shortage is becoming a global crisis due to increase in population growth and contamination of natural available resources. Only about 2.53% fresh water is available out of total water present on earth which is approximately 332.5 million cubic miles and rest of water is saline. Different types of contaminants pollute the fresh water resources as well as affect the health of humans. Millions of gallons polluted water discharged in water resources without any treatment that contaminate water resources like lakes, rivers, oceans and rivers.

Keywords: Water, sewage, pollution, contamination, saline, population.

IMPORTANCE AND DISTRIBUTION OF WATER

Water is a vital natural resource and essential for existence of life, all the economic and social activities are dependent upon the water. Most extensively occurring substance on the earth is water but the freshwater is only 2.53% and the rest is salty water. Out of 2.53% most of the freshwater is locked up in form of glaciers and permanent snow covers that is about two- third of freshwater. Further pollution play a role in reducing the percentage of freshwater, about 2 million tons of waste that is produced from different sources like human wastes, industrial and agricultural wastes is disposed per day in the waters. With time water will turn out to be the most important factor in the decision finalizing for the location of financial and economic activities. Over the past 50 years the groundwater abstraction rate has at least tripled globally. The largest consumer of freshwater is the agriculture and about 70% of the all discharged freshwater is used for agriculture (WWDR, 2009).

Detailed distribution of the earth's water is shown in fig.1 & 2. Total water supply of the world is about 332.5 million cubic miles of water but 97.5% is about the saline water and only 2.5% is fresh water. In 97.5% about 96.5% consist of oceans and 1% consist of saline groundwater and saline lakes. Whereas in 2.5% freshwater more than 68% water is locked up in glaciers and ice and another 30% of freshwater is on the ground. Fresh surface water sources such as lakes, rivers only constitute about 22,300 cubic miles which is about 1/150th of one percent of total water. Yet lakes and rivers are sources of most water people use every day (Web.2).

Distribution of Earth's Water

Fig.1: Water distribution on Earth (USGS) Web.1.

For the healthy and productive lives, over 800 million people that is, about 13% of the world's population, do not have enough water and food so in this growing population situation balance in water is the most important challenge (WWDR, 2006). The population of the world is increasing at about 80 million people a year, and to fulfil their needs in the demand of freshwater requires an increase of about 64 billion cubic meters a year (WWDR, 2009).

Groundwater and its contamination:

Water that exists in the subsurface in the fractures of rocks/soil pores or comes from the ground is called the groundwater. In most of the cases the human activities are responsible for groundwater contamination and in the dense populated areas the groundwater resources are the most vulnerable because any of their activity that produce any type of waste can contaminate the groundwater. The movement of contaminants that are released in the environment depend upon their chemical, biological and chemical properties; they either travel with water movement or not (Web.3).

One estimate of global water distribution:				
Water source	Water volume, in cubic miles	Water volume, in cubic kilometers	Percent of freshwater	Percent of total water
Oceans, Seas, & Bays	321,000,000	1,338,000,000	--	96.5
Ice caps, Glaciers, & Permanent Snow	5,773,000	24,064,000	68.7	1.74
Groundwater	5,614,000	23,400,000	--	1.7
Fresh	2,526,000	10,530,000	30.1	0.76
Saline	3,088,000	12,870,000	--	0.94
Soil Moisture	3,959	16,500	0.05	0.001
Ground Ice & Permafrost	71,970	300,000	0.86	0.022
Lakes	42,320	176,400	--	0.013
Fresh	21,830	91,000	0.26	0.007
Saline	20,490	85,400	--	0.006
Atmosphere	3,095	12,900	0.04	0.001
Swamp Water	2,752	11,470	0.03	0.0008
Rivers	509	2,120	0.006	0.0002
Biological Water	269	1,120	0.003	0.0001
Total	332,500,000	1,386,000,000	-	100

Fig.2: Water resources (Yaccup, 2012).

Substances in sewerage system that can endanger the health of community are called the sewage 'critical contaminants' and these substances are the total dissolved solids (TDS), zinc, nickel, mercury, copper, lead, cadmium and arsenic. Metals such as zinc, chromium, copper are micro-nutrients to the development of plants, and plants are able to absorb and store them in the roots but when the metals are in high concentration then they will be toxic to the plants. TDS is normally associated with the electrical conductivity and these are the total dissolved materials in the water. TDS contains positive and negative ions such as dissolved chloride, phosphate, sulphate, carbonate, bicarbonate, magnesium, sodium, calcium and other organic and inorganic matters (Tjandraatmadja and Diaper, 2006).

The main components of the wastewater at municipal level are resulting from the domestic sources compared to the other types such as industrial, commercial, storm water in case of combined drains and groundwater infiltration. The amount and strength of domestic wastewater depends on the extent and the socioeconomic behaviour of the population establishing the community. Over-all wastewater is categorized in terms of its chemical, physical, and biological configuration. Physically, wastewater can be categorized into two types; the grey water (from kitchen sinks, bath and laundry) and black water (from toilets). Chemically, the wastewater comprise of organic and inorganic composites with various gases. Organic wastes are those that

contain the carbon elements and organic components may comprise of proteins, carbohydrates, fat, surfactants, oils, greases, pesticides etc. whereas inorganic waste do not have carbon elements and are defined as mineral based compounds that may contain heavy metals, nitrogen, phosphorous, sulphur, chlorides etc. Biologically, the wastewater holds the several kinds of microorganisms (Bansode, 2002; Mgana, 2003; Tjandraatmadja and Diaper, 2006).

In the domestic wastewater contaminant can be divided into three groups: organic contaminants, suspended solids and inorganic/nutrients. In general both the suspended solids and dissolved fractions may include organic and inorganic substances (Wang et al., 2007).

To ensure the public health, chemical and biological composition must be monitored. Organic composition of wastewater consists of protein 50%, carbohydrates 40%, fats and oils 10% and trace amount of other pollutants. While the biological composition consist of approximately 10^5 to 10^8 colony forming units, 10^3 to 10^4 fecal streptococci, 10^1 to 10^3 protozoan cyst and 10^1 to 10^2 virus particles (Shon et al., 2007). Human or animal sewage, agricultural pollution or the leachate from the sanitary landfills are the main sources of biological contamination in groundwater (AL-HARTHI, 2001).

Effect of sewage contamination on humans

Billions of gallons of untreated sewage water are being put in the rivers, lakes and coastal waters every year; due to these polluted waters millions of people become ill. About 95% of sewage water discharged in the surface water without any treatment in the developing countries pollute the lakes, coastal areas and rivers (Rapaport, 1995). But the developed countries like United States, China etc. also faced the problems regarding the sewage pollution. One estimate is that wastewater production is about 1500km^3 globally and approximately eight litre of freshwater is polluted with one litre of wastewater. In the whole scenario the most affected by this pollution are the poor, about 50% of the developing countries exposed to polluted water sources and in the developing countries the most common cause of deaths and illness are water related diseases (WWDR, 2003, 2009). Due to the water related diseases about 1.6 to 2.5 million died per year and in 2002 malaria and diarrhoeal diseases were responsible for 1.3 and 1.8 million deaths (WWDR, 2006). By improving the water quality and their supply about one-tenth of the global diseases can be prevented (WWDR, 2009).

Due to swimming in the contaminated waters, every year about 1.8 to 3.5 million peoples become ill (Dorfman et al., 2004). United State which is the most powerful country in the world also face the problem due to not proper sewage system. In 1993 about 403,000 became ill due to the contaminated water supply in Milwaukee United State (Web.4). Like U.S the China also affected by the waste pollution and within three month period about 1,547 people were ill and about 468 died in Shanghai and Hongkong (Web.5). The whole world is facing a problem of water contamination and water is becoming a critical issue globally. To overcome this problem the people must think seriously otherwise in future they will face a severe problem of shortage of fresh water.

CONCLUSION

The existence of life is essentially dependent upon water. All economic and social activities are being dependent upon water resources. The water contamination issue has become global issue and life is suffering from this issue at planet earth. Wastewater situation is, day by day becoming matter of serious concern and unavoidable problem. Disposal of untreated sewage wastewater into drains and ultimately into the rivers, deteriorates the water quality and harms the human and aquatic life. Consumption of contaminated drinking water for domestic and industrial purpose ultimately affect human health. This issue is not only limited to undeveloped countries, developed countries also effected by improper water management. The indispensable actions demand globally implemented route map to overcome this water problem. The water resources should be treated with extreme care. The sewage water should be treated before disposing into streams, lakes and rivers. The waters resources being improperly treated will result in inadequate balance in natural resources. This will also affect the ecological and aquatic life at earth.

REFERENCES

- AL-HARTHI, A. A., 2001, Preliminary Environmental Assessment of the Pollution of Soil and Water at Wadi Uranah, Makkah Al-Mukarramah, Saudi Arabia: Earth Sciences, v. 13, no. 1, p. 123-150.
- Bansode, R. R., 2002, Treatment of organic and inorganic pollutants in municipal wastewater by agricultural by-product based granular activated carbons (GAC): Faculty of the Louisiana State University and Agricultural and Mechanical College in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Science in The Department of Food Science by Rishipal Rastrapal Bansode B. Tech., Osmania University.
- Dorfman, M., Stoner, N., and Merkel, M., 2004, Swimming in sewage: Natural Resources Defense Council and the Environmental Integrity Project, New York, NY [Online.] <http://www.nrdc.org/water/pollution/sewage/sewage.pdf>.

- Mgana, S. M., 2003, Towards sustainable and robust community on-site domestic wastewater.
- Rapaport, D., 1995, Sewage pollution in Pacific island countries and how to prevent it, Center for Clean Development.
- Shon, H., Vigneswaran, S., Kandasamy, J., and Cho, J., 2007 Characteristics of Effluent Organic Matter in Wastewater.
- Tjandraatmadja, G., and Diaper, C., 2006, Sources of Critical Contaminants In domestic wastewater.
- Wang, X., Jin, P., Zhao, H., and Meng, L., 2007, Classification of contaminants and treatability evaluation of domestic wastewater: *Frontiers of Environmental Science & Engineering in China*, v. 1, no. 1, p. 57-62.
- WWDR, U., 2003, Water for People, Water for Life, UNESCO Publishing.
- WWDR, U, 2006, Water, a shared responsibility: WWDR2, WWAP, Paris.
- WWDR, U, 2009, The United Nations World Water Development Report 3, Earthscan.
- Yaccup, R., 2012, The spatial characterisation of contaminant distribution found at industrial sites using combined geophysical/hydrogeological fieldstudies and laboratory modelling: Cardiff University.
- Web.1 :(<http://water.usgs.gov/edu/watercyclesummary.html>)
- Web.2: (<http://water.usgs.gov/edu/watercyclesummary.html>)
- Web.3:(www.epa.gov)
- Web.4:(http://www.americanrivers.org/assets/pdfs/Health_Risks_of_Sewage_fact_sheetb119.pdf)
- Web.5:(<http://darwin.bio.uci.edu/sustain/suscoasts/krismin.html>)